

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids. Part IV. Separation and Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III)

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A new spectrophotometric method for the micro determination of iron(III) in the presence of commonly occurring metal ions using *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (*p*-NBHA) has been described. The reagent, *p*-NBHA has the advantage that it furnishes a stable, water soluble complex which can be easily extracted into ethyl acetate.

The yellowish orange extract has a λ_{max} at 430 nm and obeys Beer's law over the range 0.4-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of iron.

The extraction is quantitative at pH 4.8-5.0. The studies on the effect of varying volumes as well as varying concentrations suggest the use of 10 ml of 0.005 *M* *p*-NBHA for the extraction. The effect of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour has also been investigated.

In the literature, a number of methods has been reported for the determination of iron(III).

Shome has recommended the use of *N*-benzoyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine as a gravimetric reagent for Fe(III), Al(III) and Ti(IV).¹ Bhaduri and Ghosh have discussed the Job's method for iron-salicylhydroxamic acid system.² Further, Gupta and Sogani have described *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine as a spectrophotometric reagent for iron.³

In the present investigation para nitrobenzohydroxamic acid is shown to be the most selective and sensitive reagent for the microgram determination of iron(III) in presence of commonly occurring metal ions.

Experimental

The reagent, para-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid, was prepared by the method described earlier⁴ (m.p. 165°, reported 165°)⁴. Its purity was checked by elemental analysis and IR and UV spectra. A 0.005 *M* reagent solution in double distilled water was used.

Ethyl acetate (BDH, AnalaR) was purified by the method of Weissberger.⁵

An aqueous solution of iron was prepared by dissolving 1 g. of ferric ammonium sulphate (E. Merck, GR) in one litre of double distilled water. Its iron content was determined volumetrically.⁶

The absorption spectra were taken on a recording spectrophotometer (model SF-10, USSR). Absorb-

ance at a particular wavelength, (430nm) was measured with a single beam spectrophotometer (model SF-4, USSR) using 10 mm cells.

General Procedure

Into a 50 ml beaker, 2 ml of iron solution and 10 ml of the reagent solution were added. This was diluted to 25 ml and the pH was adjusted to 4.8-5.0 using 0.01 *M* ammonium hydroxide and 0.01 *M* sulphuric acid. The chelate formed was transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel and 10 ml of ethyl acetate were added. The contents were shaken for 5-10 min and the organic layer was allowed to separate. The yellowish orange extract obtained was taken in an Erlenmeyer flask containing 1 g. of anhydrous sodium sulphate (BDH, AnalaR). The dried organic phase was then transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. To ensure complete recovery of iron, the above procedure was repeated with 3 ml of the reagent. The combined extracts were made upto the mark. The spectra were scanned and the absorbance was measured at 430 nm against ethyl acetate blank. The results were found to be accurate within $\pm 0.5\%$.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra

The absorption spectrum showed that the yellow orange extracts exhibit maximum absorbance at 430 nm (Fig. 1) which was reproducible. The reagent does not absorb at this wavelength. Therefore, all the measurements were made at 430 nm.

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Fig. 1.

Effect of pH

The extraction of iron-para nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was carried out at varying pH (Table 1) in the region 0.05-5.0. It was observed (Fig. 2) that the

TABLE 1. EXTRACTION OF IRON(III) *p*-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEX AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Extraction % E	Distribution ratio
0.3	0	—
0.5	0	—
1.0	0	—
2.0	0	—
3.0	10	3.89
4.0	20	6.00
4.5	50	10.00
4.7	80	18.00
4.8	100	∞
4.9	100	∞
5.0	100	∞

Fig. 2.

extraction commences at pH 4 and beyond pH 5.0, the complex precipitated. Therefore, a pH 4.8-5.0 is recommended for the quantitative extraction of iron.

Validity of Beer's law

The system obeys Beer's law over the range 0.4-30 µg/ml of iron at 430 nm and the sensitivity is 0.015 µg/cm².

Effect of reagent concentration and time

The effect of varying volumes as well as varying concentrations of the reagent on the extraction behaviour of the iron complex are presented in Table 2. The results indicate that a single extraction with 10 ml of 0.005M reagent solution was quite adequate for quantitative extraction while the extraction was incomplete with 0.001-0.004M reagent solutions. Therefore, it is recommended to use 10 ml of 0.005M para nitrobenzohydroxamic acid for extraction purposes.

Variation from 2 to 20 min. in the shaking period, revealed that 95% extraction of the coloured complex from the aqueous phase occurred in about 3 min. whereas beyond 5 min. 100% extraction could be accomplished as per the procedure detailed above.

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF REAGENT CONCENTRATION

Iron (III): 85 µg/ml pH = 4.8-5.0		
Reagent concentration 10 ⁻³ M	Volume of reagent added (ml)	Absorbance at 430 nm
1	10	0.02
2	10	0.06
3	10	0.09
4	10	0.15
5	2	0.25
..	5	0.53
..	10	0.60
..	20	0.60
8	10	0.60
10	10	0.60
..	20	0.60

The ethyl acetate extracts are stable for a few days if stored in a cool, dark place.

Effect of diverse ions

It was observed that the following ions did not interfere with the determination of 5 µg/ml of iron: Be²⁺ (20 mg), Mg²⁺ (25 mg), Ca²⁺ (50 mg), Sr²⁺ (50 mg), Ba²⁺ (50 mg), Zr⁴⁺ (30 mg), Co²⁺ (10 mg), Cu²⁺ (10 mg), Pd²⁺ (10 mg), Cd²⁺ (30 mg), Hg²⁺ (30 mg), Ni²⁺ (30 mg), Zn²⁺ (30 mg), Al³⁺ (25 mg), Pb²⁺ (30 mg), As³⁺ (30 mg), rare earths (30 mg) and 50-80 mg of chloride, fluoride, acetate and phosphate. However V⁵⁺, Mn²⁺, MoO₄²⁻ and Ti⁴⁺ are interfering with the extraction of iron.

The structure of the complex was studied using the molar ratio and Job's method. The iron to *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid ratio was found 1 : 3 in the extracted species having the following probable structure :

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